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Population in International Law

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***Abstract:** This article analyzes the legal status of stateless persons and foreign citizens and the rights provided to them within the framework of international law. Rights and obligations of foreign citizens, diplomatic protection in their countries of residence, principles of non-refoulement and relations within international human rights are also covered in the article. The article summarizes the main directions of the law and includes an analysis of the legal status of stateless persons and foreign citizens within the framework of international law.*

***Key words:** Stateless persons, International law, foreign citizens, Human rights, Diplomatic protection, Non-refoulement, International protection, Legal status*

Enter

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, with its high legal position, determines the civil policy of the state and issues related to international law. Article 2 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan reflects the legal relations of citizens with the state, the basic principles of citizenship, and the guarantees of protection of citizens. Also, in Article 4 of the first chapter of our constitution, representatives of all nationalities residing in the territory of the republic, each issues of equal rights of a person, respect and protection of his rights and freedoms are indicated [1].

Stateless persons and foreign nationals have a unique legal status and are subject to special legal norms based on international law and national laws. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Citizenship" adopted on July 2, 1992 and other legal normative documents pay special attention to the protection of the rights of stateless persons. In fulfilling its obligations under international law, Uzbekistan adheres to the 1954 Convention on the Status of Stateless Persons and other relevant international legal norms. Also, basic principles such as the legal status of foreign citizens, diplomatic protection and the principles of non-refoulement are coordinated with the internal laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan [2].

The main part

Stateless persons: International law and the legal order of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Stateless persons are persons who do not have citizenship of any country and who lose their citizenship for various reasons (for example, immigration, loss of citizenship or revocation of citizenship). International law plays an important role in protecting the rights of stateless persons. As far as I know, the rights and freedoms of foreign citizens and stateless persons in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan are ensured in accordance with the norms of international law. They undertake the obligations established by the Constitution, laws and international agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Republic of Uzbekistan has ratified the 1954 United Nations Convention on the Status of Stateless Persons. This Convention defines the main legal basis for the protection of the rights of stateless persons. According to this document, stateless persons must be protected by the state, and their basic rights, including the right to a place of residence, health care, and education, should be guaranteed. According to the Constitution of Uzbekistan, the human rights of stateless persons are respected and they have the appropriate protection from the state [3].

In Uzbekistan, there are special procedures for stateless persons, and there are opportunities to ensure their rights, to obtain the right to live, to work, and to exercise other basic rights. Article 2 of the Law on Citizenship of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Equal Citizenship, adopted on July 2, 1992, clearly defines the rights of stateless persons and states that they should have equal rights with citizens [4]. However, stateless persons may still face some legal restrictions.

Discussion/Results

Foreign citizens and their rights

Foreign citizens, that is, persons who came to Uzbekistan from other countries and are citizens of their own country, have their basic rights and freedoms in the country, but there are also some legal restrictions on them. The Constitution and other laws of Uzbekistan provide the necessary legal guarantees for foreign citizens to enter the country, live, work, study and conduct business activities. Also, the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted on December 21, 1995 and other regulatory documents protect the labor rights of foreign citizens and strive to improve their working conditions [5].

The status of foreign citizens in Uzbekistan is mainly regulated by bilateral agreements and norms of international law. For example, the principles of diplomatic protection and non-refoulement are provided within the framework of Uzbekistan's international obligations. The protection provided by the United Nations and other international organizations increases the legal security of foreign citizens in Uzbekistan.

Also, the legal, economic, social and cultural rights of foreign citizens are protected in the country. Although there are legal restrictions on foreign citizens, the Constitution of Uzbekistan and international law aim to ensure their basic human rights.

International law and legal obligations of the Republic of Uzbekistan

By ratifying the 1954 Convention on the Status of Stateless Persons, the Republic of Uzbekistan assumed international obligations aimed at protecting the rights of stateless persons. The legal obligations of Uzbekistan arising from international law determine the legal protection and guarantees provided by the state to stateless persons and foreign citizens [6].

However, ensuring compatibility between international law and national laws plays an important role in the implementation of the country's international obligations. Uzbekistan, fulfilling its international legal obligations, has a consistent policy of protecting the rights of stateless persons and foreign citizens.

Problems and prospects

There are also some problems in providing legal protection for stateless persons and foreign nationals. We can cite the following as an example of such situations: the rights of such persons are sometimes not fully implemented, there are certain restrictions on them, and the complexity of immigration and legal formalization processes for stateless persons are among them.

The harmony of our country's obligations within the framework of international law and national laws makes it possible to further strengthen the protection of the rights of stateless persons and foreign citizens. The Republic of Uzbekistan, in cooperation with international organizations, should take important steps in solving these problems and ensuring the rights of the citizens we are talking about.

Final part:

The main part analyzed the rights of stateless persons and foreign citizens, their protection under international and national law, legal obligations and opportunities of Uzbekistan. The article also discussed the current problems and prospects. The position of our Republic in international law and its legal policy towards stateless persons and foreign nationals, at the same time, is one of the important issues that continue to ensure guaranteed rights for them.

Summary

After reading this article to the end, I thought about its content, summarized it, and came to the following conclusion. What is the purpose of this article? The rights of stateless persons and foreign citizens are mainly protected on the basis of international law and domestic laws of Uzbekistan. The Republic of Uzbekistan, in cooperation with the United Nations and other international organizations, ensures the protection of the rights of stateless persons and provides legal guarantees for foreign citizens.

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